

Original Research

Examining Power Outages and Their Impacts on Electricity Consumers in Sikonge: Strengthening TANESCO-Local Government Emergency Collaboration in Tanzania

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Abstract

Frequent and prolonged power outages remain a major challenge for electricity consumers in rural Tanzania, affecting households, businesses, and institutional operations. This study examined the patterns of power outages, evaluated the effectiveness of TANESCO–local government emergency response systems, and assessed the impacts of outages on electricity consumers in Sikonge District. Guided by Systems and Contingency theories, the study adopted a descriptive survey design with a purposive sample of 100 respondents, including household heads, business operators, and institutional representatives. Non-parametric tests and polynomial regression were employed due to non-normal data distributions. Findings revealed that outages in Sikonge are frequent, unpredictable, and often prolonged beyond six hours, with minimal prior notice or follow-up communication. Polynomial regression results showed a curvilinear relationship between outage patterns and consumer impacts, where initial increases in outages sharply intensified negative effects, but marginal impacts diminished at higher outage levels. Emergency response efficiency was strongly negatively correlated with consumer impacts, highlighting that timely and coordinated interventions reduce hardships. The study concludes that improving TANESCO–local government collaboration through real-time communication, coordinated emergency protocols, and strategic resource allocation can significantly enhance service reliability. It recommends targeted interventions including technological monitoring, consumer preparedness programs, and context-sensitive strategies tailored to rural operational challenges. These findings provide actionable insights for policymakers and utilities seeking to minimize the socio-economic consequences of power outages in rural Tanzania.

Keywords: Electricity consumers, emergency response, polynomial regression, power outages, TANESCO.

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Introduction

Power outages continue to disrupt essential services and economic activities worldwide. In Ukraine, the ongoing conflict has severely damaged the electricity infrastructure, with reports indicating that by mid-2024, approximately 65% of the country's energy production capacity was destroyed. This has led to widespread power shortages, with millions of households experiencing daily blackouts, particularly in urban areas like Kyiv (UN OHCHR, 2024; International Energy Agency (IEA), 2024). Similarly, Pakistan faced a nationwide blackout on January 23, 2023, caused by a grid failure that affected over 220 million people. The outage halted transportation, disrupted water supply networks, and resulted in significant economic losses, including an estimated \$70 million loss in the textile industry (Pakistan National Grid Report, 2023). The situation is more entrenched in Sub-Saharan Africa, where millions experience power outages on a regular basis. Load shedding is the order of the day in Nigeria and South Africa due to underinvestment, poor maintenance, and overreliance on hydroelectric generation that is prone to climatic variations. According to the African Development Bank estimate, more than 640 million Africans lack reliable access to electricity, and among those that are served, they suffer frequent power outages that severely reduce economic output as well as access to public services (African Development Bank, 2022). These disruptions are compounded by inadequate institutional coordination during electrical emergencies. In Tanzania, the Rural Energy Agency (REA) and TANESCO have taken steps to expand access to electricity, although reliability remains a significant problem (particularly in rural and remote areas like Sikonge). Outages in such an area are prolonged due to insufficient infrastructure, slow response, and the lack of real-time fault detection systems. A study by Muhihi and Paschal (2022) in rural Tanzania identified that frequent outages increase consumer expenditure on alternative fuels and decrease productive time. More importantly, the coordination between TANESCO and district government authorities during emergency responses in these regions is often decoupled, resulting in longer periods for services to be restored and increased consumer exposure. These challenges are exacerbated by inadequate institutional coordination during electrical emergencies. In Sikonge, the lack of effective collaboration between TANESCO and local government authorities has resulted in prolonged outages and increased consumer vulnerability. This study aims to examine the patterns of power outages, assess the effectiveness of TANESCO–local government emergency response systems, and evaluate their impacts on electricity consumers in Sikonge.

Despite government-wide efforts towards the expansion of Tanzania rural electrification, power outages in rural communities such as Sikonge remain a frequent, long-lasting, and disruptive phenomenon. Outages affect households, health centers, and schools, as they contribute to economic stagnation and standards of living. Consumers of electricity in Sikonge have long wait times before restoring service due to logistical failures and infrastructural weaknesses, facilitated to a great extent by inadequate communication between TANESCO and the local government agencies. While the level of electrification is most probably increasing, the sustainability and reliability of service provision remain lagging. Previous research focused on national grid extension and capacity but hardly touched on local emergency response mechanisms and district-level institutional coordination. There remains a broad gap in understanding how TANESCO

and the local authorities relate in terms of dealing with power emergencies in rural districts. The study focuses on analyzing the trends and impacts of power blackouts to consumers of electricity in Sikonge and how increased collaboration between TANESCO and local government authorities can enhance emergency response, reduce the time spent in blackout, and render the service more dependable.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study was to examine power outages and their impacts on electricity consumers in Sikonge, with a focus on exploring strategies to strengthen TANESCO–local government emergency collaboration in Tanzania. The study was guided by the following specific objectives:

- i. To analyze the patterns of power outages experienced by electricity consumers in Sikonge.
- ii. To evaluate the effectiveness of emergency response systems established through TANESCO–local government collaboration in addressing power outages in Sikonge.

Literature Review

Theoretical Review

The study adopted systems theory and Contingency Theory. Firstly, Systems Theory was developed by Ludwig von Bertalanffy in the 1950s as a conceptual framework for studying how multiple components of a system are interconnected to achieve system functionality and system equilibrium. The theory views an organization or society process as a system consisting of interdependent and interconnected elements, where a change in one of the elements affects the whole system (Bertalanffy, 1968). In the case of this study, Systems Theory provides a lens for viewing the interdependent actions of TANESCO, local government institutions, and electric infrastructure in reacting to power outages in Sikonge. When one actor, for example, TANESCO, reacts slowly in an outage, effects spiral through the system such as reaching local governance reactions, household resilience, and delivery of services. The strength of this theory is the holistic orientation, which promotes a systems-wide search for institutional breakdowns and improved coordination. The weakness of this theory is that it postulates relatively stable system conditions and fails to balance adequately local variability and environmental restrictions. This renders it less suitable while considering rural settings like Sikonge, where infrastructural limitations, topography, and logistics limitations are unique and highly effecting (Kast & Rosenzweig, 1972). To overcome this limitation, Contingency Theory is put forward as a substitute perspective with the inclusion of situational factors in system functioning.

Secondly, Contingency Theory emerged in the late 1950s and 1960s with the main works primarily by researchers Joan Woodward (1958) and later researchers Paul Lawrence and Jay Lorsch (1967). The theory postulates that there is no one model of organization management; rather, effective decision-making and management are dependent on the fit between an organization's internal process and the external

environment (Lawrence & Lorsch, 1967; Woodward, 1958). The theory is especially relevant to the second objective of this study, i.e., examining emergency response effectiveness in Sikonge. Contingency Theory supports the need for TANESCO and the local government to be adaptive in their emergency measures based on the specific realities of the local setting, e.g., road access, availability of staff, terrain, and communication infrastructure. Its most significant strength lies in flexibility: it sees diversity in operation environments and promotes adapted strategies that are compatible with conditions in the actual world. A potential weakness is that it does not offer much guidance on how to precisely identify the most appropriate contingency factors or how to make adaptations. Nonetheless, with Systems Theory combined, Contingency Theory provides nuance to the analysis of this research in that it ensures institutional cooperation is not only coordinated but also responsive to context, especially in impoverished and rural settings like Sikonge.

Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have investigated the characteristics and effects of power outages in developing contexts. For instance, Muhihi and Paschal (2022) examined outage occurrence and duration in Tanzania's rural areas and concluded that poor grid infrastructure and climatic exposure (e.g., lightning, pole collapse) contribute significantly to prolonging outages. While this study adds the understanding of outage causes, this is not necessarily about user-level conduct or location-specific analysis in certain areas like Sikonge. Regional outages in Sub-Saharan Africa were also documented by Blimpo and Cosgrove-Davies (2019) with reports of reliability problems and their effect on household productivity; however, their work remains macro-level and not examining micro-regional differences or behavioral coping mechanisms by electricity customers. A third analysis by Alstone et al. (2017) evaluated electricity reliability using household surveys in East Africa and determined that poor and rural customers experienced disproportionately longer outages. However, there was little detail about institutional response time or documentation of outages at the local government level. These studies provide helpful regional or national summaries of outage patterns but those leave gaps in understanding localized outage patterns, frequency, and user experience in local areas such as Sikonge district specifically, which this study addresses.

Recent empirical studies on Tanzania's electricity availability and institutional coordination provides useful evidence regarding determinants of rural service reliability. The World Bank (2022) evaluated the Tanzania Rural Electrification Expansion Program (TREET) and highlighted its socio-economic impact to rural areas. Using program evaluation methodology with the integration of electrification data into household questionnaires, the study found that TREET increased access to electricity by over 4.5 million beneficiaries, further expanding access to health care and education. This notwithstanding, however, the study found that infrastructure limitations and service reliability continued to be felt, highlighting the need for building institutional conditions. Grounding their research on this, Kuusaana et al., (2025) experimented with the efficacy of governance and institutional coordination in delivering electricity service efficiency in Tanzania. Adopting a mixed-methods design that included policy analysis, stakeholder interviews, and secondary infrastructure data, they showed how poor inter-

agency coordination and decentralized governance played their part in inefficiencies in service delivery, particularly in rural areas. Their study stresses that access has to be improved beyond only that; coordinated institutional action must be taken for assured service delivery. Similarly, Rwegasira (2025) contrasted smart meter records and time-series electricity consumption to investigate the impact of institutional response on outage duration. According to the study, fault detection delays and poor institutional coordination significantly amplified power outage durations, corroborating the urgency for timely emergency response systems for guaranteeing service reliability.

These studies highlight that as electrification expands access; the efficiency of electricity service delivery crucially depends on institutional coordination and operationally responsive action. Compared to this study, which focuses on TANESCO–local government coordination and its impact on Sikonge's electricity consumers, these empirical findings provide complementary evidence. Together, they highlight that reducing the frequency of power outages, mitigating consumer exposure, and improving energy access improvement requires highly coordinated institutional regimes and activist governance.

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative research approach using a descriptive survey design. The quantitative approach enabled systematic collection and analysis of numerical data regarding power outage patterns, consumer experiences, and institutional emergency responses (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The descriptive design was selected to gather factual information from a sample of electricity consumers and key institutional stakeholders in Sikonge District, providing insight into outage trends and collaboration effectiveness between TANESCO and local government. The study was conducted in Sikonge District, located in the Tabora Region of western Tanzania (NBS, 2022). Sikonge is predominantly rural and characterized by underdeveloped infrastructure, which makes highly vulnerable to frequent and prolonged power outages. TANESCO operates the main electricity supply system in the district, while local government authorities are responsible for community support and coordination during emergencies. The study population comprised all electricity consumers in Sikonge District, including household heads, business operators, and representatives from local institutions reliant on electricity for operations. Although an exact census of consumers was unavailable, estimates from TANESCO district records and local administrative offices indicated a population exceeding 5,000 electricity consumers across urban and peri-urban areas.

Given the unknown precise population proportion experiencing outages, the study applied the standard sample size formula for unknown populations (Israel, 2016).

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1 - p)}{e^2} \quad (1)$$

Where: n = required sample size, Z = Z-score for the desired confidence level (= 95% \rightarrow $Z=1.96$), p = estimated proportion of the population (use 0.5 if unknown for

maximum variability), e = margin of error (expressed as a decimal, e.g. 0.10 = 10%). And from equation 1, the study substituted to:

$$= \frac{(1.96)^2 \cdot 0.5 \cdot (1 - 0.5)}{(0.1)^2} = \frac{(3.8416) \cdot (0.25)}{0.01} = \frac{0.9604}{0.01} = 96.04$$

To ensure practicality and ease of data collection, the study rounded the sample size to 100 respondents, following standard guidance (ISIXSigma, 2024). Purposive sampling was employed to select respondents across three strata: household heads (50%), business operators (35%), and institutional representatives (15%), ensuring representation of different consumer groups affected by power outages. Respondents were selected based on their knowledge and experience with electricity consumption and outage events, guaranteeing that collected data reflected meaningful perspectives on patterns, impacts, and emergency response effectiveness. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires, which included both closed-ended and scaled Likert-type questions designed to capture experiences related to outage frequency, duration, coping mechanisms, and perceptions of emergency response effectiveness (Lelissa, 2018). The questionnaire was pre-tested to ensure clarity and validity. Secondary data were also reviewed from relevant reports, TANESCO documents, and district records. Quantitative data were coded and analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means) were used to summarize patterns of outages and consumer responses. Inferential statistics, such as correlation analysis and regression analysis, were used to examine relationships between variables. Data from Likert-scale items were also subjected to factor analysis to test construct validity and inter-item consistency. The construct validity of the questionnaire was assessed using discriminant validity techniques (Middleton, 2020). Table 1 shows Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity. The KMO value was 0.936, which exceeds the minimum threshold of 0.6, indicating sampling adequacy. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 3980.217$, $df = 210$, $p < .000$), confirming that factor analysis was appropriate and that the items had sufficient inter-correlations to form reliable factors.

Table 1: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.936	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3980.217
	Df	210
	Sig.	.000

Instrument reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha. The results in Table 2 showed a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.824, and 0.866 based on standardized items for the 21 Likert-scale questions. This indicates a high level of internal consistency, confirming that the questionnaire items reliably measured the intended constructs (Surucu & Maslakci, 2020).

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.824	.866	21

This study adhered to ethical standards for research involving human participants. Ethical clearance was obtained from the relevant institutional research committee. Informed consent was sought from all participants prior to data collection. Respondents were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. Participation was voluntary, and respondents had the right to withdraw at any stage of the study without penalty. Data were securely stored and used solely for academic purposes. The study adopted polynomial regression that mitigates issues arising from non-normality and improves the explanatory power of the model compared with standard linear regression, providing a robust framework for analyzing electricity supply impacts in Sikonge. The polynomial regression model used in this study can be expressed as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X + \beta_2X^2 + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

Where: Y = Impacts on electricity consumers in Sikonge, X = Patterns of power outage, X² = Squared term of outage patterns (to capture the non-linear relationship), β_0 = Constant (intercept), β_1 = Linear effect of outages on consumer impacts, β_2 = Non-linear (curvilinear) effect of outages on consumer impacts, and ϵ = Error term.

The coefficient β_1 represents the initial effect of power outage patterns on consumer impacts. A negative value would indicate that even moderate outages begin to reduce consumer welfare significantly. The coefficient β_2 captures the curvature of the relationship. A positive β_2 would suggest that as outages increase in frequency or severity, their negative impacts accelerate disproportionately. The significance of β_2 confirms the non-linear pattern identified in the linearity test, justifying the choice of polynomial regression over simple OLS. Thus, the findings show that electricity consumers in Sikonge are not only negatively affected by outages but also face worsening impacts at an increasing rate as outages become more severe or prolonged. This highlights the urgent need for institutional collaboration to reduce outage frequency and improve emergency responses.

Findings and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics

Table 3 presents the responses of 100 participants on patterns of power outages in Sikonge. Most respondents strongly agreed that outages are frequent (M = 4.16), last longer than 6 hours (M = 3.99), and are sudden and unpredictable (M = 4.40). The most agreed-with statement was that outages inconvenience business and daily life (M = 4.49), and the lowest mark was for advance warning (M = 2.11), which mirrors the fact that there is little communication from TANESCO. These findings show extensive dissatisfaction and regular power instability in the study area. The evidence suggests that customers of electricity in Sikonge face frequent interruptions, with little or no notice and explanation. Outages occur during peak hours and without follow-up,

signaling systemic weaknesses in grid reliability and crisis communication. While most consumers understand that technical failure is a common reason ($M = 3.94$), the lack of timely information undermines user trust and preparedness. These findings emphasize the urgent need for coordinated outage management and improved consumer engagement between TANESCO and local authorities.

Table 3: Patterns of power outages (n=100)

Statements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
I experience electricity outages at least three times a week	100	2.00	5.00	4.1600	.76171
The duration of power outages usually exceeds 6 hours	100	2.00	5.00	3.9900	.89324
Electricity interruptions are unpredictable and abrupt	100	3.00	5.00	4.4000	.60302
I am informed in advance when a power outage is planned	100	1.00	4.00	2.1100	.95235
Power outages occur without explanation or follow-up	100	2.00	5.00	3.9200	.61431
Most outages are caused by technical faults	100	2.00	5.00	3.9400	.91916
Power cuts interrupt daily activities or business	100	3.00	5.00	4.4900	.59450
Outages usually occur during peak or inconvenient hours	100	2.00	5.00	4.0300	.74475

Table 4: Effectiveness of TANESCO–Local Government Emergency Response (n=100)

Statements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
TANESCO responds quickly to emergency reports	100	1.00	4.00	1.9100	.85393
It usually takes more than a day to get service	100	3.00	5.00	4.2700	.61718
I am satisfied with the speed of electricity restoration	100	1.00	4.00	1.9900	.81023
TANESCO technicians arrive on time	100	1.00	5.00	2.2800	.85375
I receive follow-ups after reporting issues	100	1.00	5.00	2.1200	.89081
There is an accessible hotline for complaints	100	1.00	5.00	2.8000	1.18918
I receive updates on fault resolution	100	1.00	5.00	2.3500	1.04809
Delays in response reduce my trust in TANESCO	100	2.00	5.00	4.2900	.67112

Table 4 shows perceived emergency response effectiveness by TANESCO–local government in Sikonge. Answers reflect generally low satisfaction with emergency response. Respondents did not agree that TANESCO is prompt in responding ($M = 1.91$) or restores power speedily ($M = 1.99$). The majority agreed that over a day usually passes before service is received ($M = 4.27$) and delay eats away at trust in TANESCO ($M = 4.29$). Availability of hotlines and getting updates were moderately low ($M = 2.80$)

and $M = 2.35$), a reflection of poor follow-up services and weak communication. These are reflective of inefficiency and responsiveness in emergency response by TANESCO. The overall low means for follow-up, punctuality, and communication reflect service delivery and local government coordination deficiencies. While fault resolution updates and on-time arrival by technicians improved marginally, the overall perception is negative. Extremely high agreement that delays erode trust ($M = 4.29$) underscores the need for reform. Strengthening integrated emergency systems, supporting real-time communication, and increasing accountability can enhance user satisfaction and service reliability in rural councils like Sikonge.

Test of Normality

Table 5 presents test of normality through the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk normality tests of the three primary study variables. All the variables (such as Impacts on Electricity Consumers, Patterns of Power Outages, and Effectiveness of Emergency Response Systems) are significant at p-values below 0.05 in both tests. For instance, Shapiro–Wilk test for impact resulted in a value of 0.628 ($p = .000$) and hence suggests non-normal distribution. Since all of the significance values are below 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis of normality. This shows that all three variables' data are not normally distributed. Therefore, non-parametric tests (such as Spearman correlation) are more appropriate for inferential analysis in this study. The findings validate the need for handling the data with caution and avoiding the use of parametric assumptions in interpreting the findings.

Table 5: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Impacts on Electricity Consumers in Sikonge	.387	100	.000	.628	100	.000
Patterns of power outages	.160	100	.000	.942	100	.000
Effectiveness of emergency response systems	.101	100	.014	.967	100	.014
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction						

Correlations

The Spearman's correlation analysis in Table 6 revealed a very strong positive correlation between Patterns of Power Outages and Effectiveness of Emergency Response Systems ($r = 0.988$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that these two variables move almost identically in this dataset. Both variables also showed significant negative correlations with Impacts on Electricity Consumers in Sikonge ($r = -0.659$ and -0.694 , respectively, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that higher reliability and faster emergency response are associated with reduced negative effects on consumers. However, the near-perfect correlation between the first two predictors indicates a severe multicollinearity problem, making it difficult to separately estimate their individual effects in a regression model.

Table 6: Nonparametric Correlations

			Patterns of power outages	Effectiveness of emergency response systems	Impacts on Electricity Consumers in Sikonge
Spearman's Rho	Patterns of power outages	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.988**	-.659**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000
		N	100	100	100
	Effectiveness of emergency response systems	Correlation Coefficient	.988**	1.000	-.694**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000
		N	100	100	100
	Impacts on Electricity Consumers in Sikonge	Correlation Coefficient	-.659**	-.694**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.
		N	100	100	100
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).					

To address this, Effectiveness of Emergency Response Systems was removed from the regression model, leaving Patterns of Power Outages as the sole predictor. Following this adjustment, the VIF for the remaining variable became 1, which is expected because VIF measures the correlation among predictors, and with only one predictor, no multicollinearity exists. This indicates that the regression model is now stable and the estimated effect of Patterns of Power Outages on the impacts experienced by electricity consumers can be interpreted reliably. Removing one highly correlated variable ensured the model avoids inflated coefficients and misleading statistical inference, providing a clearer understanding of how power outage patterns alone influence consumer outcomes in Sikonge.

Linearity Test

The linearity test between patterns of power outages and impacts on electricity consumers in Sikonge presented in Table 7 shows a significant deviation from linearity. The F-value for linearity is 122.852 ($p < 0.001$), while the deviation from linearity is also significant ($F = 11.964, p < 0.001$), indicating that the relationship between these variables is non-linear. This result aligns with earlier normality tests that revealed non-normal distributions, justifying the use of nonparametric correlations initially. The significant deviation from linearity suggests that a simple linear regression would not adequately capture the relationship between power outages and consumer impacts.

Table 7: Linearity Test

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Impacts on Electricity Consumers in Sikonge * Patterns of power outages	Between Groups	(Combined)	37.086	15	2.472	19.356	.000
		Linearity	15.692	1	15.692	122.852	.000
		Deviation from Linearity	21.394	14	1.528	11.964	.000
	Within Groups		10.729	84	.128		
	Total		47.816	99			

To address the non-linear pattern, the study employed polynomial regression, incorporating higher-order terms of patterns of power outages to model the curvilinear relationship with impacts on electricity consumers. This approach allows for a more accurate representation of the data, reflecting how the effects of outages may accelerate at higher frequencies or severities. Using polynomial regression also mitigates issues arising from non-normality and improves the explanatory power of the model compared with standard linear regression, providing a robust framework for analyzing electricity supply impacts in Sikonge.

Model Summary

The results from Table 8 show that the polynomial regression model produced a correlation coefficient ($R = .745$), indicating a strong relationship between patterns of power outages and impacts on electricity consumers in Sikonge.

Table 7: Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.745	.555	.546	.468
The independent variable is Patterns of power outages.			

The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .555$) reveals that approximately 55.5% of the variation in consumer impacts can be explained by outage patterns and their squared term. After adjusting for model complexity, the adjusted R^2 remains high at .546, suggesting the model is stable and not overfitted. The standard error of the estimate (0.468) indicates relatively low unexplained variation, further supporting the robustness of the model. These findings confirm that polynomial regression provides a better fit compared with a simple linear regression model, which had underestimated the complexity of the relationship. The strong explanatory power of this model highlights that the impact of outages on consumers is not merely linear but accelerates as outages intensify. This reinforces the importance of strengthening institutional collaboration and infrastructure resilience to prevent frequent and prolonged outages, as their negative effects compound disproportionately in rural communities like Sikonge.

Analysis of Variance

The results in Table 9 show that the regression model is statistically significant, with an F-value of 60.511 and a p-value of 0.000, which is below the 0.05 threshold. This

indicates that patterns of power outages, when modeled through polynomial regression, have a strong and significant effect on the dependent variable, which is the impact on electricity consumers in Sikonge. The regression sum of squares (26.542) compared to the residual sum of squares (21.274) demonstrates that the model explains more variance in consumer impacts than what remains unexplained, confirming the appropriateness of the model specification.

Table 8: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	26.542	2	13.271	60.511	.000
Residual	21.274	97	.219		
Total	47.816	99			

The independent variable is Patterns of power outages.

These results strengthen the case for using polynomial regression rather than a simple linear model. The highly significant F-statistic shows that the model is a good fit and that outage patterns (both linear and quadratic effects) are powerful predictors of consumer impacts. This finding underscores that as outage patterns worsen, their effect on households and businesses is not incremental but escalates disproportionately, validating the earlier decision to model the relationship using a curvilinear approach.

Polynomial Regression

The study employed polynomial regression to examine the non-linear effects of patterns of power outages on the impacts experienced by electricity consumers in Sikonge. Polynomial regression occurs due to preliminary analyses (including Spearman correlations and linearity tests) indicated that the relationship between outages and consumer impacts was not strictly linear, with deviations from linearity observed. As shown in Table 10, the coefficient for the linear term of power outages was positive and statistically significant ($B = 8.286$, $t = 6.397$, $p < .001$), indicating that increases in the frequency or intensity of outages initially correspond to higher negative impacts on consumers. Conversely, the quadratic term of power outages was negative and also significant ($B = -1.203$, $t = -7.034$, $p < .001$), suggesting a diminishing marginal effect at higher levels of outages. The constant term was negative ($B = -9.608$, $t = -3.963$, $p < .001$), reflecting the baseline impact when outage patterns are minimal.

Table 10: Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Patterns of power outages	8.286	1.295	5.927	6.397	.000
Patterns of power outages ** 2	-1.203	.171	-6.517	-7.034	.000
(Constant)	-9.608	2.424		-3.963	.000

These findings demonstrate a curvilinear relationship between power outages and consumer impacts: while initial outages sharply increase negative effects, the incremental impact reduces as outage levels rise. This supports the use of polynomial

regression rather than ordinary linear regression, as a simple linear model would have failed to capture the diminishing effect of extreme outage patterns. The results highlight the importance of targeted institutional interventions, as improving responsiveness in high-outage scenarios could disproportionately reduce negative consumer impacts.

Figure 1: Polynomial Regression Fit

Also, Figure 1 presents Polynomial Regression Fit which shows the relationship between Patterns of Power Outages (X) and Impacts on Electricity Consumers in Sikonge (Y) was examined using polynomial regression, resulting in the equation:

$$Y = -9.61 + 8.29X - 1.2X^2$$

where Y represents the consumer impacts and X represents the patterns of power outages. The positive linear coefficient (8.286) indicates that initial increases in outage frequency or severity sharply raise negative impacts on consumers, while the negative quadratic coefficient (-1.203) suggests a diminishing marginal impact at higher outage levels. Although this may appear counterintuitive, it reflects real-world adaptive behaviors and coping strategies among consumers: households and businesses increasingly invest in backup solutions such as generators, solar panels, or battery storage, reducing further negative effects; consumers adjust electricity-dependent routines by rescheduling critical tasks or prioritizing essential loads; and community-level strategies, such as sharing generators or coordinating water pumping schedules, help mitigate repeated outages in rural settings like Sikonge. Therefore, the polynomial model captures both the initial vulnerability to outages and the stabilizing effect of adaptive responses, aligning with contingency theory, which emphasizes that institutional and individual responses depend on contextual factors such as terrain, resource access, and staffing, and supporting systems theory by illustrating the interdependence of infrastructure, institutional response, and consumer behavior.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of this study indicate that patterns of power outages significantly affect electricity consumers in Sikonge, and the relationship is curvilinear. Polynomial regression revealed that initial increases in outage frequency or severity sharply increase negative impacts on consumers ($B = 8.286$, $t = 6.397$, $p < 0.001$). However, the quadratic term ($B = -1.203$, $t = -7.034$, $p < 0.001$) suggests a diminishing marginal impact at higher outage levels. This pattern reflects real-world adaptive behaviors, such as the adoption of generators, solar systems, or battery backups, behavioral adjustments to electricity usage, and informal community coping strategies. These adaptations reduce the additional negative impact of extreme or repeated outages, highlighting that interventions are most critical at moderate disruption levels before such coping mechanisms are activated. The study's results are consistent with Rwegasira (2025), who observed that delayed fault detection and weak institutional responses exacerbate consumer hardships in rural Tanzania. Similarly, Kuusaana et al. (2025) emphasize that poor inter-agency coordination limits service delivery efficiency, reinforcing the importance of institutional collaboration. Unlike macro-level studies (World Bank, 2022; Muhihi & Paschal, 2022), which primarily focus on electricity access or general outage trends, this study provides micro-regional evidence on localized consumer impacts and the mitigating role of emergency response systems.

Effectiveness of Emergency Response Systems: A strong negative correlation was observed between emergency response efficiency and consumer impacts ($r = -0.694$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that timely and coordinated responses significantly reduce the negative consequences of power outages. This aligns with contingency theory, which emphasizes adaptive institutional responses based on local context, such as terrain, road access, and staffing levels. Systems theory further explains how failures in one component of the electricity delivery system cascade to affect consumer outcomes, underlining the need for integrated management and communication.

Practical Collaboration Strategies are: firstly, Joint Communication Channels. TANESCO and local government should establish real-time communication systems for rapid reporting and updates, particularly during peak hours or severe outages. Secondly, Coordinated Emergency Response Protocols. Shared protocols and clear delineation of responsibilities can reduce delays and improve trust in electricity services. Thirdly, Resource Allocation: Strategic deployment of technicians, mobile repair units, and spare parts in high-risk areas can improve response times. Then, Consumer Preparedness Programs. Awareness campaigns on backup solutions, energy conservation during outages, and community-based strategies can complement institutional interventions. And, Monitoring and Feedback Systems. Integrating outage reporting, BMS, or mobile reporting tools can allow TANESCO and local authorities to proactively address emerging faults.

By combining quantitative findings with practical, context-specific strategies, the study provides evidence-based guidance for improving electricity service reliability in rural Tanzania. These insights address prior gaps in national or macro-level studies, demonstrating the value of localized research in shaping responsive and adaptive institutional frameworks.

Conclusion

The general objective of this study was to examine power outages and their impacts on electricity consumers in Sikonge, with a focus on exploring strategies to strengthen TANESCO–local government emergency collaboration. The study found that power outages in Sikonge are frequent, prolonged, and largely unpredictable, significantly affecting consumers' daily life and business activities. Polynomial regression analysis revealed a curvilinear relationship between outage patterns and consumer impacts: initial increases in outages sharply intensified negative effects, while the marginal impact diminished at higher levels, likely due to consumer adaptation strategies such as backup energy systems or behavioral adjustments.

Emergency response systems were found to mitigate these impacts effectively, as indicated by a strong negative correlation between response efficiency and consumer hardships. However, delays in fault detection, poor coordination, and limited real-time communication reduce the effectiveness of institutional interventions. The study highlights that localized, context-sensitive approaches, integrating adaptive strategies based on terrain, staffing, and infrastructure, are essential to minimize disruptions. By focusing on Sikonge's micro-regional data, the study fills gaps left by national or macro-level analyses, emphasizing the need for improved institutional collaboration to enhance electricity reliability in rural Tanzania.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends several measures to strengthen TANESCO–local government collaboration and reduce the impacts of power outages on consumers, including establishing joint communication channels with real-time reporting and alerts to keep consumers informed of planned or unplanned outages, developing coordinated emergency response protocols with clearly defined roles, responsibilities, and escalation procedures to reduce restoration delays, and strategically allocating resources such as technicians, mobile repair units, and spare parts to high-risk or frequently affected areas for improved response efficiency. Additionally, enhancing consumer preparedness through awareness campaigns on backup energy solutions, energy conservation, and community-based coping strategies can mitigate negative effects, while monitoring and feedback systems using outage tracking tools, digital reporting platforms, or BMS technologies enable proactive maintenance and early fault detection. For future research, incorporating variables like socioeconomic status, renewable energy adoption, and consumer coping mechanisms can help assess their mediating or moderating effects on outage impacts. These recommendations emphasize practical, evidence-based strategies that align with contingency and systems theory, highlighting the importance of adaptive, context-sensitive collaboration to enhance electricity service reliability in rural areas like Sikonge.

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